

GRAMMATICAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Narzullayeva Firuza Olimovna

The lecturer at the department of English literature and translation studies at Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: *This article deals with the interlinguistic lexical and grammatical transformations, and types of transformation in Uzbek and English languages.*

KEY WORDS: *translation, correspondence, morphologic, syntactic, complete, partial, absence of syntactic correspondence, substitution, transposition, omission, supplementation.*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, written and spoken translations have played a crucial role in interhuman communication.

In the English-speaking world, this discipline is now generally known as ‘translation studies’, thanks to the Dutch-based US James S. Holmes (1924–1986). In his key defining paper delivered in 1972, but not widely available until 1988, Holmes describes the then nascent discipline as being concerned with ‘the complex of problems clustered round the phenomenon of translating and translations’ (Holmes 1988b/2004: 181). By 1995, the time of the second, revised, edition of her *Translation Studies: An Integrated Approach*, Mary Snell-Hornby was able to talk in the preface of ‘the breathtaking development of translation studies as an independent discipline’ and the ‘prolific international discussion’ on the subject (Snell-Hornby 1995, preface). Little more than a decade later, the editors of the second edition of the *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation* comment on ‘new concerns in the discipline, its growing multidisciplinary, and its commitment to break away from its exclusively Eurocentric origins, while holding on to the achievements of the past decades’.

METHODS

In order to attain the fullest information from one language into another one is obliged to resort to numerous interlinguistic lexical and grammatical transformations.

Grammatical transformations are as follows:

- 1) Substitution
- 2) Transposition

3) Omission

4) Supplementation

The cited types of elementary transformations as such are rarely used in the process of translating. Usually they combine with each other, assuming the nature of complex interlinguistic transformations.

By substitution we understand the substitution of one part of speech by another or one form of a word by another. Consequently there are two kinds of substitution constituting a grammatical type of transformation: substitution of parts of speech and the grammatical form of a word. Transformation by substitution may be necessitated by several reasons: the absence of one or another grammatical form or construction in the Target language; lack of coincidence in the use of corresponding forms and constructions as well as lexical reasons – different combinability and use of words, lack of a part of speech with the same meaning.

An example of the substitution of a word-form may be the interpretation of the meaning of the grammatical category of posteriority of an English verb, which is presented in two particular meanings: absolute posteriority (He says he will come) and relative posteriority (He said he would come). Uzbek and Russian verbs do not possess word-forms of this kind and communicate their meaning with use of other grammatical means:

У келишини айтяпти. Он говорит, что придет.

У келишини айтди. Он сказал, что придет.

In Uzbek the meaning of this category is expressed by a substantivized participle ending in -жак or by the infinitive ending in -(и)ш; in Russian the future tense form of a verb is used.

There are two types of substitution of parts of speech: obligatory and non obligatory. The obligatory substitution is observed when in the Target language, there is no part of speech corresponding to that used in the Source language. e. g. the English articles.

RESULTS

Apart from other functions the article may function as an indefinite or demonstrative pronoun, a numeral, and may be used for emphasis. In cases of this kind it is necessary to substitute them with functionally— adequate means of expression in Uzbek and Russian.

E.g. when we were in Majorca, there was a Mrs. Leech there and she was telling us most wonderful things about you. (A. Christie)

Биз Мальоркада бўлганимизда, у ерда ақандайдир миссис Лич бор эди. У бизга сиз тўғрингизда жуда кўп қизиқарли нарсаларни айтиб берди.

Когда мы были в Мальорке, там была некая миссис Лич, которая рассказывала очень много интересного о вас. (А. Кристи)

In Uzbek and Russian an indefinite pronoun is used for translating the indefinite article.

Non obligatory substitution is a substitution undertaken by the needs or demands of the context:

The climb had been easier than he expected.

Кўтарилиш у кутгандан осонроқ бўлди.

Подняться оказалось легче, чем он ожидал.

A noun in the English sentence is substituted by infinitives in the Uzbek and Russian languages.

“Transposition (as a type of transformation used in translations) is understood to be the change **of** position (order) of linguistic elements in the Target language in comparison with the Source language”.

Transposition (change in the structure of a sentence) is necessitated by the difference in the structure of the language (fixed or free order of words etc.), in the semantic of a sentence, and others.

DISCUSSION

There are two types of transpositions; transposition (or substitution) of parts of a sentence and transposition occasioned by the change of types of syntactic connection in a composite sentence. Examples:

1. Transposition of parts of a sentence

e.g. If he ever gets married, his own wife will probably call him “Ackley”.

(J. Salinger, *The Catcher in the Rye*, 3).

Наверное, и жена будет звать его “Экли”- если только он когда-нибудь женится.

2. Transposition occasioned by the change of types of syntactic connection in a composite sentence

e.g. The silver saucer clattered **when he replaced the pitcher.**

(H. Lee, *To Kill a Mockingbird*, 3)

Он быстро поставил кувшин, даже серебряная подставка звякнула.

He took another look at my hat **while he was cleaning them.**

(J. Salinger, *The Catcher in the Rye*, 3)

Он их чистил, а сам смотрел на мою шапку.

e.g. A big scarlet Rolls Royce had just stopped in front of the local post office.

(A Christie.)

Маҳаллий алоқа бўлими олдида кизил рангдаги катта Рольз Ройс автомашинаси тўхтади.

Уместного почтового отделения остановилась комфортабельная автомашина алого цвета Рольз Ройс.

In the English sentence the semantic core is expressed by the indefinite article while in Uzbek and Russian it is assigned to the second and third places accordingly.

When translating English compound sentences into Uzbek and Russian, the principal and subordinate clauses may be transposed. This is explained by the fact that the order of words in compound sentences does not always coincide in the languages considered. Compare:

A remarkable air of relief overspread her countenance as soon as she saw me.
(R. Stevenson)

Мени кўриши биланоқ, унинг юзида енгил тортганлик аломати пайдо бўлди.

Как только она увидела меня, на её лице выразилось чувства облегчения.

As a type of grammatical transformation – omission is necessitated by grammatical redundancy of certain forms in two languages.

He raised his hand.

У кўлини кўтарди.

Он поднял руку.

Addition, as a type of grammatical transformation, can be met with in cases of formal inexpressiveness of grammatical or semantic components in the language of the original text.

CONCLUSION: Also, there was an awkward hesitancy at times, as he essayed the new words he **had learnt**.

Баъзида у яқиндагина ўрганган янги сўзларини талаффуз қилишга ҳозирланиб, тўхтаб қоларди.

Иногда он запинаясь, готовясь произнести слова, которое он только недавно выучил.

The meaning of the verbal form is expressed in Russian by the words «только недавно» and in Uzbek by the adverb “яқиндагина”

It must be emphasized that the division into lexical and grammatical transformations is, to a great extent, approximate and conditional. In some cases a transformation can be interpreted as one or another type of elementary transformation. In practice the cited types of lexical and grammatical transformations are seldom met with in “pure form”. Frequently they combine to form complex transformations.

REFERENCES:

1. Файзиева, Азиза Анваровна. "ОРИЕНТАЦИОН КОНЦЕПТУАЛ МЕТАФОРАЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ." In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION", vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 26-29. 2022.

2. Sirojova, Z. (2022). Functional Study of Syntactical Relations of Compound Sentences in Uzbek Linguistics. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 22(22).
извлечено от

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8069

3. Sirojova , Z. . (2022). SYNCRETISM OF SYNTACTICAL RELATIONS IN UZBEK COMPLEX SENTENCES. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(11), 119–122. извлечено от
<https://www.inacademy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/4694>

Narzullayeva F. LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS A COMPLEX SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 17. – №. 17.

4. Narzullayeva Firuza. “English Phraseological Units With Somatic Components”. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE, Vol. 1, no. 1, Oct. 2020, pp. 29-31,

5. NARZULLAYEVA FIRUZA MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF SOMATIC LEXICAL GROUPS IN ENGLISH ЯЗЫК И КУЛЬТУРА Ежегодный альманах: материалы XV международной научно-практической конференции, Челябинск, 2020.

6. Narzullaeva Firuza, POLYSEMY AND ITS TYPES IN THE NON-RELATED LANGUAGES. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, VOLUME 12 May 2021, pp.379-383.

7. Narzullayeva , F. O. (2023). NOMINATIVE AND EXPRESSIVE FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE STUDY. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(6), 35–40. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/idea/article/view/886>